

SYMBOLS IN THE WORLD MODERN POETRY

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Abstract. Following article deals with symbolism and symbols, that are distinguished as terms in literature field. While symbolism denotes the name of a literary movement, a symbol is interpreted as a poetic movement. At the same time, these concepts are mutually exclusive. Because symbolism is based on a symbol. The term symbol is used as a synonym for a symbol. It is formed on the basis of a specific sign. This term comes in a broad and narrow sense. The broad meaning of a symbol is seen in its use in other sciences and art, and the narrow meaning is seen in its use in connection with artistic creativity.

Keywords: symbol, poetry, modern, symbolism

Introduction. The symbol in literature corresponds to that anything can be chosen for the symbol. This literary device can be a word, an object that the author uses in the text to draw the readers' attention to the message. In world literary studies, a number of works on symbols have been carried out as follows: in English literary studies, it is covered in the studies of such scholars as Arthur Simons, Michael Fekos, Michael Gibson, T.Ezebube; in Russian literary studies D. Merezhkovsky, V. Bryusov, Vilenkin, Teternikov, Z. Gippius, Z.Minsk, Z.Snejko; among Uzbek scholars the works of G. Ayimbetova, Nurboy Abdulhakim, Zuhra Mamadalieva are important in this regard.

One of the main purpose of this work is to reveal the theoretical foundations of the studies in which the poetics of symbols are studied in world literature, as well as to determine the types of symbols used in world modern poetry. Russian scientist N.I. Snejko defines a symbol as follows: "A symbol is a multidimensional concept, each field of knowledge reveals its meaning based on the object of study". [11,23]

This idea shows that the symbol is used not only in literature, but also in various fields. Continuing his opinion, he writes: "The method of content analysis, in which the most common units are separated and considered productive, is used to identify common, nationally specific, special features in symbol poetry. They organize the symbolic space of the poetic text and seem to create a symbol. They have different natures. Space and time understood as the coordinates of the picture of the world can be called existential, based on the concepts of the physical image of the world.

In literature, a symbol, as a unique poetic tool, performs the function of figurative, emotional-expressive expression of artistic thought. Symbols are

widely used in poetry. The thought expressed through them acquires a deep vital meaning and philosophical essence. The symbol is combined with various related phenomena. In particular, it has signs that are harmonious with metaphor and simile. However, unlike them, a symbol is used figuratively both within the context and in its own meaning. Metaphor, on the other hand, conveys only a figurative meaning. The animal world serves as an object for simile.

Based on the above, the article presents the term symbol, its lexical meaning, and definitions in literary dictionaries. On this basis, the specific features of this poetic tool are identified. The issue of attitude to this literary phenomenon in literary studies is studied. The classification of symbols according to their content is presented and their features are clarified. At the same time, the symbol is compared with related phenomena - metaphor and simile, their common and different aspects are highlighted.

Materials and methods. In the content coverage of the topic, the materials of several poets were widely used, which were important in the study of symbols in poetry. It is well known to the readers that he had a special attitude to nature - the world of plants, not only in his special poems, but also in his entire work. It is clearly noticeable that the poets approached the world of flora with extremely high point of view of giving it a symbolic meaning. Methods such as comparative analysis, objectivity, systematic approach have also been used from a methodological point of view.

Results and discussion. A poem is a product of lyrical experience. There are special means of expressing it powerfully and effectively, and we can include symbols here. The theory of symbols is widely developed in world literature. In particular, the views of English, Russian and Uzbek poetry confirm our opinions. First, let us pay attention to the definition of the term in dictionaries.

In literature, symbolism and symbol are distinguished as terms. Symbolism is the name of a literary trend, and a symbol is interpreted as a poetic movement. At the same time, these concepts are mutually exclusive, because symbolism is based on symbols.

“Meanings of a symbol: 1. Something that is used or considered as representing something else; a material object that represents something, often something insignificant; an emblem or sign. 2. A letter, number, or other symbol or combination of letters, or the like, used to designate something. 3. A word, phrase, image, or the like, which has a complex of interconnected meanings and is separable from the symbolic meaning, is a part of the symbolized thing, and is

accepted as performing its normal function, represents the symbolized thing. It usually derives its meaning mainly from the structure in which it appears, and is usually distinct from the sign". [4]

This idea is based on the fact that the symbol is formed on the basis of the sign. In fact, two things or concepts are connected by interrelated meanings. For example, in poetry, a bird is a symbol of freedom. In this sense, the free flapping of a bird's wings in the air is associated with freedom. Another dictionary defines a symbol as "representing an object or action that represents something abstract in the mind". [6]

"Therefore, a symbol is a figurative expression of an abstract concept in the mind. Symbolism is the representation of one thing for another by means of a person, object or idea". (The writer's dictionary) There is a stream of symbolism in literature, the main requirement of which is to rely only on symbols to describe life and the person in it. The symbol is characteristic of fiction in general. In this sense: "Symbol is an object, action or idea that means something other than itself, often has a more abstract nature". [16] So, colors, objects, things, flora and fauna world are chosen for the symbol. The figurative significance of the chosen object is ascertained. Certain words, things, or concepts evoke certain associations. We are able to decipher another meaning for them. These items are referred to as symbols. One of the objects in this is a white dove, which stands for freedom and peace. In other words, there is a connection between the ideas of peace and white doves. Anything that represents something else, whether directly or indirectly, is a symbol. A symbol is frequently used in literature and art to represent an abstract idea that is expressed through an item. It could be a person, an animal, a building, or a plant. For instance, a crow represents death and destruction, but a crimson rose represents love. It appears that the symbol can be anything. It could be a person, a building, an animal, or a plant. The symbolic meaning of the chosen object is ascertained by analyzing its essence. That object therefore conjures up a variety of associations. This is also true of the literary sign, therefore any choice can be made for the symbol. It could be a person, a building, an animal, or a plant. The symbolic meaning of the chosen object is ascertained by analyzing its essence. As a result, that object evokes various associations.

In fact, the symbols will have a national and universal meaning. In literature and art, the symbol went through several stages:

1. The first stage of symbolic cognition is related to the mythological level of consciousness (rituals, traditions).

2. A person's symbolic reflection of the events and processes of the surrounding reality corresponds to the beginning of the development of writing.

3. With the development of society, the emergence of culture and civilization, it is time theoretically interpret the symbol as a cultural phenomenon at the bottom of philosophy.

Currently, the symbol is considered as a universal cultural phenomenon, which is renewed in various fields of knowledge, both in the natural and humanities.

Symbolism in poetry fulfills a number of important tasks, enriches the poetic experience, and allows poets to convey deeper meanings and feelings beyond the literal meaning. In this regard, the following can be shown:

1. Symbols allow poets to convey abstract and complex ideas in an effective way. By using symbols, poets illuminate feelings, concepts, and themes that may be difficult to express directly.

2. Symbols add depth and layers of meaning to a poem, transforming it from a simple description or story into a multidimensional work that engages readers intellectually and emotionally.

3. Symbols have the power to evoke strong feelings and vivid images. They can evoke associations and memories in readers, creating a deeper and more personal connection with the poem.

4. Some symbols have universal meanings and are recognized in different cultures. These symbols help poets explore themes and ideas that resonate with people of different backgrounds, creating a sense of shared human experience.

5. Symbols create ambiguity and mystery in poetry. This leaves room for readers to find layers of meaning and discover new insights with each reading.

6. Skillful use of symbols increases the aesthetic impact of poetry.

7. It allows the poet's experiences and feelings to be expressed figuratively.

8. Political and social symbols in poetry can be used to criticize the norms of society, express dissatisfaction or advocate social changes.

9. Symbols can be repeated in poems. They provide integrity in the work.

Conclusion. In general, in a symbol, an image is created through comparison. It is expressed in three different ways: it appears through the characters, objects or events of the work. Colors, objects, things, the world of flora and fauna are chosen for the symbol. Based on the selected object, the figurative meaning is determined. Also, anything can be chosen for the symbol. Currently, the symbol is considered as a universal cultural phenomenon, which is renewed in various fields of knowledge, both in the natural and humanities.

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